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Holistic, omnipresent, resilient services
for future 6G wireless and computing ecosystems

D6.1 Impact Creation Strategy and Plan

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Abstract	This document presents a sound and well-articulated communication strategy that has been developed to increase awareness of the HORSE vision, objectives, and achievements and a stakeholders engagement strategy for an open, participatory, and sustainable community. The document describes the strategic approach, sets the overall framework, and provides directions regarding all planned communication and engagement activities and will be regularly updated to match the evolving needs and opportunities.
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SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
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Classified C-UE/ EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444	
Classified S-UE/ EU-S	EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444	

- * *R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)*
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc
DMP: Data management plan
ETHICS: Deliverables related to ethics issues.
SECURITY: Deliverables related to security issues
OTHER: Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

Executive summary

The document at hand presents a comprehensive communication, dissemination, and community-building strategy that has been developed to maximise the impact of HORSE and ensure that the following communication-related project objectives are met:

- Establishing a distinctive and recognizable brand identity that will support promotional and marketing efforts.
- Achieving broad visibility and raising awareness about HORSE and its results.
- Support other tasks and WPs in attracting new stakeholders to the HORSE ecosystem by creating meaningful communications.
- Produce appealing promotional artefacts and provide support in event organisation.
- Establishing liaisons with relevant initiatives.

In addition to setting the communication framework, the strategy provides clear directions for the consortium and can be viewed as a guiding document for project partners, so that they can better align on the communication objectives and planned dissemination activities.

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Abbreviations

IP	Internet Protocol
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
SNS JU	Smart Network and Services Joint Undertaking
EU	European Union
WP	Work Package
SNS	Smart Network and Services
6G	6th Generation
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
6G IA	6G Industrial Association
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
ADRA	AI, Data and Robotics Association
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
IRTF	Internet Research Task Force
5GPPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
....	

1 Introduction

1.1 HORSE in a Nutshell

The main focus of the HORSE project is a holistic research approach aimed to design, develop and validate an autonomous, self-evolving and extendable 6G-ready architecture providing a human-centric approach to security workflows, by enabling top-down, bottom-up and end-to-end security solutions.

6G technologies, benefitting from softwarisation, Gb/s speed and sub-THz communications paradigms, open up opportunities for developing new and innovative network management strategies while navigating the evolution toward disaggregation, new software-based paradigms in architecting and operating future connectivity platforms, and embracing features of computing, automation and smartness, trust, privacy and security. Supported by this technology evolution, as the vision of new, smart and innovative capabilities is becoming a reality, superb user experience is expected even in presence of mobility and resource volatility. However, the fundamentally new and unknown features of advanced, disaggregated, virtualized and multi-vendor 6G based infrastructures, challenge the security and resilience design to the next level, by managing the unknown, complex and highly versatile infrastructures as they evolve. Indeed, the future deployment of 6G networks is inextricably connected with an integration of diverse hardware elements and infrastructures, thus leading not only to a highly heterogeneous environment, but also to functions and features that cannot be anticipated at the time of design. The vision of HORSE in this complex scenario, is to deal with the technology solutions, and system evaluation not yet foreseen, towards an omnipresent, smart and secure network service provisioning in the future network-of-networks landscape. To this end, HORSE proposes a novel human-centric, open-source, green, sustainable, coordinated provisioning and protection evolutionary platform, which can inclusively yet seamlessly combine advancements in several domains, as they get added to the system (e.g., predictive threats detection, proactive business-wise threats and breaches mitigation actions, programmable networking, semantic communications, Network Function Virtualisation (NFV), intent-based networking, AI-based techniques, cross-layer management of physical layer features, etc.).

1.2 Purpose of the Document

This document, prepared in the context of WP6 (Impact Creation), defines the communication, dissemination, and community building strategy and describes the activities HORSE is (or will be) pursuing to guarantee broad visibility, adequate promotion, and uptake of project results. The plan provides a framework for different outreach activities that will be carried out throughout the project by different project partners with the ambition of achieving the following objectives:

- Defining and implementing a comprehensive and effective set of dissemination and communication activities to create awareness about project activities and results.
- Facilitating exploitation and sustainability of project outcomes.
- Designing, establishing, and implementing a framework for the monitoring and assessment of the impact created by the project.
- Creating and growing the community around the project activities and foster interactions with other initiatives and 6G SNS projects on similar topics.
- Creating liaisons within the 6G, SNS JU communities.

This document is dynamic and can be edited by all project partners within the framework for updates and adjustments overseen by Martel Innovate. The plan will be periodically evaluated and adjusted throughout the project. Major results and updates will be included in periodic reports.

1.3 Structure of the Document

The sections of this deliverable are organized in the following manner:

- Section 1 introduces the project HORSE, its vision and mission, and provides insights into the technological environment in which the project operates.
- Section 2 presents project communication and dissemination objectives, strategy and plan, the channels, outlines a coherent plan to reach a broad audience.
- Section 3 emphasizes the means and activities foreseen during the entire course of the project. This section describes the various types of dissemination tools and activities in more detail.
- Section 4 is dedicated to liaisons and collaboration with relevant projects and initiatives and a plan for dissemination activities with respect to publications, conferences, events, etc.
- Section 5 describes the indicators that will be used to assess the impact of project achievements.
- Section 6 concludes the document.

2 Outreach and Impact Creation Strategy and Plan

An efficient and effective dissemination and communication strategy can ensure short and long-term success of a project and the impact it can create. Therefore, promotion, dissemination, exploitation and engagement activities are key to achieving envisioned impact with HORSE. A comprehensive plan of activities will be closely coordinated among the various WPs to effectively engage all target stakeholders in the 6G wireless ecosystem.

HORSE will engage in dissemination, communication, and community building with investors/corporates, communication network providers, SMEs and startups, researchers in industry and academia, innovators, operators, policy makers and users, as well as relevant 6G communities and projects as appropriate.

A comprehensive and well-structured set of dissemination activities are aimed to raise awareness and encourage uptake of developed concepts, technologies, use cases, and results. This will include offline and online communications, digital presence, participation in and organization of events, contributions to standardization, interactions and liaisons with relevant initiatives and projects.

For this purpose, HORSE puts in place a comprehensive set of measures, which are aimed at maximizing the envisaged impact in a coordinated way: by tightly integrating the communication and dissemination activities with exploitation and sustainability work.

A set of dedicated outreach and communication activities will ensure that the below project objectives are met.

- Establish a distinctive and easily recognizable identity that will support promotional and marketing efforts;
- Raise awareness about HORSE results and benefits and ensure the project's broad visibility and uptake among the European 6G smart networks and services and wireless communications communities;
- Reach, stimulate, and engage a critical mass of relevant stakeholders to ensure that the project results are effectively showcased, leading to validation, improvement, and possible further adoption of the developed technologies and concepts;
- Facilitate sustainability and exploitation of the project's outcomes and promote the development of innovative solutions based on the HORSE technologies and concepts;
- Support the key players' engagement strategies and activities, while providing visibility and echo to the SNS JU community within the European ecosystem and beyond;
- Foster impactful contributions to relevant scientific domains, open source and standardization bodies as appropriate;
- Create and grow the community around the project and foster interactions with other initiatives and 6G SNS and EU-funded projects on similar topics facilitating discussion, scaling up, and experience sharing;
- Design and implement a framework for the monitoring and assessment of the impact created by HORSE.

2.1 Outreach and Impact Creation Phases

HORSE's outreach and impact creation strategy and plan includes offline and online communication, digital presence, participation in and organization of events, interaction with

other research and innovation projects within the domain, as well as liaisons with relevant stakeholders and related SNS JU, 6G IA, NetWorldEurope and EU research and innovation initiatives. The core structure of the envisaged plan has been broken down into three stages.

Figure 1: HORSE Impact Creation Phases

Outset (M1-M09): Awareness creation and communication foundation

Scope: The development of dissemination, communication, and community building strategy and plan, including the refinement and mapping of target groups, selection of dedicated communication tools and community building activities, and informing all relevant stakeholders about the HORSE scope and objectives. This phase is also dedicated to defining the liaisons and interaction mechanisms with targeted projects, relevant communities like SNS JU, 6G IA, ENISA, ADRA, BDVA, AIOTI, HPC, FIWARE and GAIA-X and standardization bodies like 3GPP, ETSI, IRTF and 5GPPP.

- **Measures:** Bespoke brand identity and project website, communication and dissemination strategy and plan, event calendar, project introduction flyer, project presentation (slides), project social media channels, and introducing the project in some communities, e.g. SNS JU communication task force, participation to at least one conference/event presenting HORSE’s objectives, first edition of e-Newsletter, organization of first internal workshop at M4 for use-case requirements generation and discussion.

Formation (M10-M23): Community Outreach and initial results dissemination

Scope: Run stakeholders’ engagement campaigns to generate interest in HORSE’s activities and outcomes and set a solid foundation for the planned dissemination activities and encourage them to provide support in promoting the project. Plan event participation and organization including the project workshops, set a solid foundation for the planned dissemination, showcasing and policy making / intervention activities.

- **Measures:** Slide-based presentations of first project results, first project video, regular animation of social media channels, publishing news items, sending out periodical newsletters, and participation in selected events, organization of 1st technical workshop and engaging in clustering activities for dissemination.

Boosting engagement (M24-M36): Global outreach and sustainable impact

Scope: Engaging and supporting the adoption and deployment of the concepts and tools offered by HORSE through dedicated promotional activities ensuring the project’s uptake and

strong and durable impact for commercial purposes and policymaking. Promotion of the piloting and validation activities, publishing further scientific publications, open accessible project results from the project website and open platforms.

- **Measures:** Promotional materials in various forms, online publications, established liaisons with relevant initiatives, news items, press releases, technical reports, additional editions of the e-newsletter, interviews, videoclips, dedicated webinars, training materials, participation in events, infographics presenting project results, organization of events and workshops with other SNS and/or HE funded projects, organization of final technical workshops, demos in events, inputs to standardization.

2.2 Reaching a Broad Audience

The diverse target groups HORSE plans to address, which have a very different level of knowledge and expectations with respect to 6G and Cybersecurity research, require the definition and use of tailored mechanisms and tools to be able to properly convey the right message for each audience. The list of target stakeholders identified at the time of proposal preparation includes:

- **Industry players including those from the use-case sector:** Telco operators, ICT vendors/providers, software developers, SMEs, innovators and start-ups across various verticals, especially cybersecurity.
- **Public authorities initiatives, policy makers:** Public organizations and civil society organizations in cybersecurity and security initiatives. Policymakers engaged in defining regulatory frameworks and data governance mechanisms and digital security and privacy protection organizations.
- **Scientific community, research, academia across 5G/6G, cybersecurity, AI, etc:** scientists and researchers at research institutions and universities.
- **European and global initiatives:** ENISA, ADRA, AIOTI, FIWARE, BDVA, HPC, GAIA-X
- **Relevant R&I projects within SNS JU, 6G IA, NetWorldEurope, IoT, Cloud, AI, security:** researchers, professionals, experts within the parameters of projects.
- **Open-source communities and standardization bodies:** Open-source communities, such as CNFC, the Linux Foundation, and Apache (Arrow, Parquet, Ranger, Atlas, Egeria). Standards Developing Organizations (SDOs), such as ETSI, 5GPP, IRTF etc.
- **General public:** Private individuals interested in communication networks, wireless networks and technologies, AI, cybersecurity, cloud edge technologies.

For each of these groups, customized communication and dissemination activities will be pursued as part of the communication and dissemination strategy and plan, in order to deliver a consistent message to all target audiences, while ensuring to properly translate the HORSE value proposition in a way that can more effectively contribute to engage the different players.

2.3 Primary Communication and Dissemination Channels

A broad array of communication and dissemination channels is used to effectively reach the target groups and to maximize awareness of the overall project's work and outcome. The synergy of HORSE dissemination is generated through seamless connected online and offline communication activities. Both online (e.g., website and social media) and offline channels (e.g. events) will be used to disseminate HORSE related activities and project actions throughout Europe and beyond. In addition, all the networks and multipliers channels allow the

partners of HORSE to raise the visibility of the project’s achievements and to reach a critical mass of stakeholders, developers, contributors, integrators, researchers and relevant key players for an efficient implementation of the project work plan.

The dissemination channels used to reach each target group are detailed in Table 1:

Table 1: Communication & Dissemination Channels per target group

Channel/ target group	Technology professionals in business	Public org.	Innovators & researchers	Open source & standardisation bodies	Policy makers	Civil society	General public
Website	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Social media	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Newsletter	X	X	X		X	X	X
Conference	X	X	X	X			
Own events	X	X	X	X	X	X	
External events	X	X	X	X	X		
Scientific publication		X	X		X		
Marketing materials (eg, flyers)	X	X	X		X	X	

3 Means and Activities

3.1 Brand Identity

Brand identity consists of visible assets, such as logo, colour palette, and typography that are created to portray a certain image and distinguish the brand. It defines how those who come in contact with the brand perceive it and influences their opinion about it. Good brand identity provides unique and memorable assets and a unified and consistent 'look and feel' across all outlets (electronic and printed visual media).

Figure 2: Creating HORSE brand identity

The design of the HORSE brand identity began during the proposal preparation. The following assets have been developed as part of the HORSE brand:

- Colour palette
- Logo and icon with different variations
- Typography
- Templates for deliverables and presentations

Figure 3: HORSE Logo

3.1.1 HORSE Colour Palette

There is no doubt that first impressions count. The main reason why they are so important is that they last well beyond the first time we come in contact with something new. This is due to the primacy effect, which is the tendency to remember the first things in a sequence best. Having this in mind, the creative team leveraged the findings of colour psychology and colour theory and started with a foundational element of any brand identity – colour, as this is usually the first thing stakeholders see. To determine the palette that works best for HORSE, the team looked at the associations of colours to clearly convey HORSE brand personality and showcase optimism, creativity, and the project’s commitment to trustworthiness. When choosing the colours, it was also important that they worked together in harmony, which is why the team opted for an analogous brand colour palette.

A main palette of 4 colours based on the logo colour scheme. These are the colours of the logo gradient and elements. In combination with the main colours palette, two more greyscale colours can be used.

For slide presentations and deliverables: the colour of standard elements has been defined and locked in the respective templates, as those documents are likely to be mainly edited outside design departments.

Figure 3: HORSE Colour Palette

3.1.2 Logo

The main idea behind the logo (Figure 3) was to synthesize a continuous model connecting the secure, resilient, connectivity paradigms. It reflects the main idea behind the HORSE toolkit. A textual part with the name of the project has been added to support the ideogram.

3.1.3 Typography

HORSE’s brand uses the open-source fonts from Google Fonts: Comfortaa (Bold version) for headings and Roboto (Regular and Bold versions) for body copy and headings too. The usage of other versions of the fonts are allowed. This applies to the website, presentations and all promotional material.

For deliverables, the system font Arial (only Regular and Bold versions) will be used instead, to avoid missing font issues, as those documents are likely to be mainly edited outside design departments. It could be used also for presentations in case the two brand fonts are missing.

3.1.4 Templates

To ensure that all deliverables produced within the scope of the project follow the same structure, a Word document template has been created. The template will be used by all partners to guarantee visual consistency of the layout, format, and boilerplate text across all deliverables. The document at hand also follows the defined template.

A PowerPoint presentation template, figure 4 with the glimpse of the template, has been created to be used by all partners when preparing their presentations for external events, meetings, etc.

Figure 4: HORSE Presentation template front and back covers

In addition, a press release template, figure 5 with a glimpse of a press release, has been created as well to be used by all partners when preparing a press release for important activities and news.

Figure 5: HORSE Press release

3.1.5 Brand Guidelines

Brand guidelines are a book of rules as to how the brand should appear, which is important for consistency. Building and maintaining a strong brand identity helps to be recognizable and remembered. HORSE brand guidelines consist of the following components:

- the logo variations with the ‘dos and don’ts’,
- colour palette (PMS, CMYK, RGB, and HEX),
- typography/font for use in emails, print, and websites.
- EU acknowledgement and recognition for scientific publications and promo materials.

The detailed brand guidelines can be found in Appendix A.

3.2 Internal Communication Tools

The HORSE consortium has created multiple mailing lists for internal communication purposes.

- Mailing list for each work package
- Mailing list for the Executive Board
- Mailing list for the General Assembly
- Mailing list for the entire consortium

The coordinating team (CNIT) has provided an intranet for the consortium, below figure 6 with the intranet homepage, an internal working and shared space for document repository, contacts of the persons involved in HORSE project, dedicated Microsoft Teams link for each work package and boards to host and join the periodic calls.

Figure 6: HORSE intranet and document repository

3.3 Project Website

Launched at the end of January 2023, M1 of the HORSE project, the HORSE website (<https://www.horse-6g.eu/>) has been developed to act as an information hub presenting the project's goals, objectives, activities, the pilots, achievements, news and events. The website has a landing pillar page that highlights the main traits of the projects, this pillar page concept is more attractive for the website as it gives the visitor the main attributes of the project without having to leave the home page, as well as it ranks high on SEO. On top of the home page are also menu items which showcase the activities, outputs, features of the project. The wireframe of the website had been shared with the consortium during the project Kickoff meeting in order to gather feedback for content. Most of the pages in the website have already been published and the rest will be published at a later stage, when respective content/output is available and/or published. Below Figure 7 shows the wireframe of the HORSE website and Figure 8 shows the look of the website on multiple devices.

Figure 7: HORSE website wireframe

Figure 8: HORSE website

The website consists of the following menu items:

- **Home:** The landing page is published and consists of components which also links to dedicated web pages in the website, eg. use-cases give a snapshot of these features, and a button is added that directs the user to a more detailed description on a dedicated webpage.
- **About:** This menu item has components that give information about the project, the consortium, the software which the project (HORSE tools) will be producing and the use-cases.

- **Latest news:** Under this menu item, is information about the news from the project and the relevant and upcoming events for the project.
- **Events:** This menu item show-cases the upcoming events where HORSE will be participating or is relevant for the topic.
- **Resources:** This menu item consists of the different outputs of the project, eg, public deliverables, presentations, promo materials, publications, press releases, videos. It has been decided that the “Software” sub-menu will be just an item on the menu which will redirect the user to the public “Github” repository of the project. The consortium is in the process of discussion about the public software repository and once this is set up, it will be linked via the website.
- **Contact:** This page allows the user to get in touch with the project representatives.

At the time of writing of this deliverable, the website counted 965 visitors that generated 2,200 pageviews and that had an average visit duration of 2 minutes, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: HORSE website analytics

As one of the main dissemination channels and dynamic tools, the website will undergo major streamlining, and it will be continuously updated throughout the lifetime of the project. Since its inception, Martel is working on supporting the traffic to the website through:

- **SEO** – the website traffic will increase progressively throughout the project thanks to the implementation of techniques oriented at driving organic traffic, such as the use of appropriate keywords and the production of engaging and shareable content.
- **Link building** – synergies between the project’s website and the partners’ websites, as well as with other relevant agents of the sector (targeted stakeholders) will be created, encouraging the exchange of links.

It should be noted that all the information and emails collected are protected under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). HORSE will only contact those who have submitted their

inquiries and send newsletters only to those who have explicitly requested to receive them. Any person who has subscribed will be allowed to remove their email address from the list upon request. Additionally, the website provides information on the stored data and how they are used in alignment with the GDPR under the Privacy policy link (footer of the webpage).

The project website serves as a comprehensive platform to assess the effectiveness of HORSE's communication and dissemination efforts. This is achieved by carefully analyzing web analytics data. The HORSE website utilizes Matomo as their web analytics software platform to obtain detailed reports on their communication campaigns, website visits, acquisitions, and overall website performance. Importantly, Matomo aligns with European GDPR standards and safeguards the ownership of collected data.

Last but not least, HORSE opted for an environmentally responsible website hosting platform, which has been designed to be as energy efficient as possible to limit the unnecessary waste of resources. The web hosting provider, GreenGeeks, puts back three times the power consumed into the grid in the form of renewable energy.

3.4 Social Media Channels

Various social networks have been established as marketing tools and linked to the project website. Their goal is to promote the activities and outputs of the project and build a network around the project's work while encouraging a discussion on swarm computing centric technologies and platforms, and other related topics. Below is an overview of the social media channels created for HORSE.

Twitter

Twitter is a dynamic social network that covers the news in real-time at a global level. HORSE Twitter account, @HORSEProjectEU, was established in January 2023, before the kickoff meeting of the project. At the time of writing, it counts **101** followers.

Figure 10: HORSE Twitter homepage

The Twitter account is used to promote the project, as well as to share relevant news and events and project related partners updates. HORSE uses Twitter to establish meaningful connections with an active and relevant audience, such as academics, policymakers, and the general public. By following relevant users throughout the duration of the project, HORSE will not only gain access to relevant content and updates but also acquire more followers. Examples of appropriate hashtags: #5G, #6G, #wirelesscommunication, #cybersecurity, #communication etc.

To maximize the visibility of the project on social media channels, HORSE follows the accounts of relevant initiatives and projects and retweets their updates when appropriate. Below is the list of social media accounts and hashtags that is used for HORSE social media activity:

Table 2: Relevant social media handles and hashtags

<p>Hashtags</p>	<p>#HorizonEU #6G #5G #wirelesscommunication #MobileNetwork #cybersecurity #DigitalDecade #SNS #EUResearch #FutureConnectivity</p>
<p>Twitter handles</p>	<p>@HorizonEU @DigitalEU @EU_Commission @6G_SNS @ITU @NetTechEU @one6GGlobal</p>
<p>LinkedIn handles</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association • Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) • EU Digital & Tech • EU Science, Research and Innovation

LinkedIn

LinkedIn is currently the main business network in the world with more than 150 million users. HORSE established its [LinkedIn page](#) in January 2023, before the official kickoff of the project. At the time of writing, the account has **137 followers**. The profile supplements the website by helping to drive traffic to the site and offers a way to promote the project to a broader audience. Partners’ LinkedIn pages, as mentioned in Table 3, are mentioned when appropriate to create positive visibility exchanges. Besides, Martel intends to promote HORSE across relevant LinkedIn groups to grow the project’s audience.

Figure 11: HORSE LinkedIn page

Table 3: HORSE Consortium social media accounts

Partner name	LinkedIn account	Twitter
CNIT	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cnit---consorzio-nazionale-interuniversitario-per-le-telecomunicazioni/	@CNIT_TLC
Atos	https://www.linkedin.com/company/atos/	@Atos
Telefonica	https://www.linkedin.com/company/telefonica/	@Telefonica_En
Ericsson	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ericsson/	@ericsson
TUBS	https://www.linkedin.com/school/tu-braunschweig/	@tuBraunschweig
NKUA	https://www.linkedin.com/school/national-kapodistrian/	@uoaofficial
SUITE5	https://www.linkedin.com/company/suite5/	@suite5eu
UPC	https://www.linkedin.com/school/universitat-politecnica-de-catalunya/	@la_UPC
Martel	https://www.linkedin.com/company/martel-gmbh/	@Martel_Innovate

Partner name	LinkedIn account	Twitter
EFACEC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/efacec/	
HOLO Light	https://www.linkedin.com/company/hololightgmbh/	@Holo_LightGmbH
ZORTENET		
SPHYNX	https://www.linkedin.com/company/sphynxsts/	@SPHYNXTS
8BELLS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eight-bells-ltd/	@8Bells_research

3.5 Newsletter

The consortium has scheduled 2 HORSE newsletters per year providing updates on project activities and results. More specifically, the newsletters will contain information on the upcoming tasks, attended and organized events, as well as any relevant news and announcements from individual partners. All consortium members will provide relevant information to ensure that the content of the newsletter is engaging, accurate, and timely.

In case of an important information/announcement to be made, a newsflash will be sent to the newsletter subscribers. The difference between a newsletter and a newsflash is in the number of announcements made. A newsletter is a longer compilation of news and events, activities and outputs of the project whereas a newsflash is information about just 1 activity/output. A newsflash enables giving more attention to a news piece as compared to that being part of a longer newsletter.

The design of each newsletter will be aligned with HORSE brand identity and will be fully responsive to ensure its full readability on any device. The technology behind the newsletter will provide enough flexibility to be adapted to the communication needs of the project. All issued newsletters will be uploaded on the website.

A mailing list based on subscription has been created, giving the possibility to share the newsletter via mass mailing. A registration functionality allowing interested visitors to subscribe to the newsletter is already available on the project website. Martel will ensure that the above mentioned actions comply with the requirements of the GDPR. Mailings with invitations to relevant workshops and webinars, consultations, and any other information that cannot wait for the newsletter publication will be sent to the same database used for the newsletter.

The first newsletter of the project will be published in the second quarter of 2023 giving general information about the project, the pilots, highlighting the consortium and reports from events participation. If there are some technical updates, an editorial article on the technical update will be included.

3.6 Videos

HORSE has established a YouTube channel of its own and has its first introductory video published featuring the Coordinator CNIT and the Media and communication partner Martel Innovate who give a brief outline of the HORSE project, the technology components it's going

to use and its relation in the SNS JU community. This video has been published via HORSE's social media channels and also appears on the home page as well as the dedicated page for "Videos" on the website.

Figure 12: HORSE first video snapshot

Apart from the partners interviews, events participation, and marketing related videos, HORSE plans to publish videos to provide updates on the project, disseminate its vision and achievements, and promote the experts and other stakeholders involved. Producing and sharing such content will support awareness creation, stakeholder engagement, and the uptake of project results and the developed technology.

3.7 Promotional Materials

During the lifetime of the project, a number of documents, deliverables, technical reports, posters, webinars, and presentations will be produced. All outputs of the project can and will be used for the promotion of the project. Promotion in terms of raising awareness about the project in the scientific as well as industrial community and promotion in terms of exploitation of the technological products of the project.

Some promotional materials that will be produced during the course of the project are:

- A leaflet, updated at least once, to reflect the project's evolution. A general overview flyer has already been produced and published which was circulated at the events, ETSI conference 2023, MWC 2023 and EuCNC 2023.
- 2 HORSE posters have already been produced and printed for the poster presentation at events, ETSI conference 2023 and EuCNC 2023. These posters can be accessed from the HORSE website under the dedicated page for "Promo materials" in the "Resources" web page.
- A roll-up as and when HORSE will participate/organize a session at an event.
- Different promotional materials will be designed and printed as per the requirement and the kind of event, e.g., bookmarks, booth giveaways (if/when HORSE participates as an exhibitor in an expo kind of event).

Figure 13: HORSE poster for ETSI Conference 2023

Figure 14: HORSE poster for EuCNC 2023

The HORSE project aims to create a holistic research approach aimed to design, develop and validate an autonomous, self-evolving and extendable 6G-ready architecture providing a human-centric approach to security workflows, by enabling top-down, bottom-up and end-to-end security solutions.

OBJECTIVES

- Analyse foreseeable 6G scenarios
- Design end-to-end security solutions
- Develop a human-centric programmable platform
- Deploy predictive AI technologies
- Characterise user's profile and 6G system as a digital twin
- Design an interface as "Human-In-The-Loop"

CONSORTIUM

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Holistic, omnipresent, resilient services for future 6G wireless and computing ecosystems

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ARCHITECTURE

USE-CASES

Secure Smart Light Rail Transit Systems

Management and orchestration, with high availability, of several systems, applications and end-to-end services, supported by equipment on tram stops, trams and in the Command Center.

Remote Rendering to Power XR Industrial

Multiuser collaboration allows Industry 4.0 to solve complex issues efficiently, giving them the opportunity to meet in a virtual common space to collaborate and share virtual 3D objects.

Figure 15: HORSE flyer

The EU emblem is the single most important visual brand used to acknowledge the origin and ensure the visibility of EU funding and co-funding. In the case of the SNS JU programme, as a co-funded EU partnership, the guidelines are the use of the association of the EU emblem together with the SNS logo, and all HORSE materials will follow the dedicated guidelines:

Figure 16: EU emblem and 6G SNS Logos compositions

Project slide deck

A dedicated project slide deck has been created to outline and promote the project's vision, objectives, use-cases, activities and consortium. The Slide Deck has been used at presentations and it's available on the [website](#) as PDF and the editable powerpoint version is available on the shared drive for all partners to use at their events presenting HORSE. The presentation is available in Appendix B.

4 Plan of Activities (M1 - M36)

4.1 SNS Joint Undertaking & SNS OPS

HORSE is a Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) project (stream B), a Public-Private Partnership that aims to facilitate and develop industrial leadership in Europe in 5G and 6G networks and services.

Through the coordination with the SNS OPS CSA supporting the collaboration and synergies of the SNS JU projects, HORSE already started actively collaborating with other 6G SNS projects. Several HORSE partners have been or are actively involved in 6G SNS Phase 1 and have a long track record in establishing fruitful liaisons with other projects. This liaison will allow HORSE to be aware of the ongoing activities and strengthen the mutual developments within the 6G and wireless communication era.

The collaboration with the 6G SNS JU is already bringing concrete results in the form of:

- HORSE is already featured among the SNS projects on the [6G SNS website](#) and it's actively contributing to and echoing SNS JU social media efforts.
- The HORSE participation to the [SNS Lunchtime Webinar 3 – Introducing the SNS projects](#), as part of the SNS Lunchtime Webinar series presenting the Stream B1 & B4 projects addressing: Architecture & Secure Services and Security.
- **SNS JU Communication Task Force Meetings** take place monthly to align among all SNS Projects communication and dissemination representatives on common activities, knowledge sharing and updates on the SNS initiatives.

4.2 Synergies with Related Projects and Initiatives

The HORSE project will provide important learnings and elaborations as well as insights and recommendations focusing on designing and validating key technical enablers for 6G wireless communication. Therefore, securing proper engagement in dissemination, communication and community building towards industry, including network operators and infrastructure providers, SMEs, standardization bodies, researchers, as well as citizens, public authorities and initiatives, policy makers and relevant 6G, wireless networks and cybersecurity communities such as 6G IA, ETSI, 3GPP and more is very important to cover different perspectives.

Thanks to the participation of partners in several ongoing projects, associations and initiatives, targeted liaisons and synergies will be leveraged to ensure HORSE's broad outreach, fostering effective HORSE uptake and validation of the project's platform.

The [6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association \(6G-IA\)](#) is the voice of European Industry and Research for next generation networks and services. Its primary objective is to contribute to Europe's leadership on 5G, 5G evolution and SNS/6G research. The 6G-IA represents the private side in both the 5G Public Private Partnership (5G-PPP) and the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU). In the 5G-PPP and SNS JU, the European Commission represents the public side.

As mentioned in section 4.1, the participation to 6G SNS JU and 6G IA activities has been planned and listed, allowing HORSE to be aware of the ongoing activities and strengthen the mutual developments within the 6G era. The 6G-IA brings together a global industry community of telecoms & digital actors, such as operators, manufacturers, research institutes, universities, verticals, SMEs and ICT associations.

[SNS OPS](#) is a Coordination and Support Action aimed at supporting the operations of the 6G Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking. The planned work is to facilitate the activities of the European SNS Initiative, as outlined in the SNS contractual partnership. Collaborating on common technological challenges and audiences will be key to ensure broad visibility and knowledge sharing among all projects and initiatives under the SNS OPS.

[One6G](#) is a membership organization focused on evolving, testing and promoting next generation cellular and wireless technology-based communications solutions. By supporting global 6G research and standardization efforts, the goal is to accelerate its adoption and overall market penetration, while addressing societal and industry-driven needs for enhanced connected mobility. The shared network of the One 6G initiative, alongside the knowledge base will on one hand result in additional inputs for the project (both on technical and business-related manners), and will also create broader awareness amongst the key stakeholders of the 6G domain.

4.3 Workshops and Conferences

The organization of events in the form of webinars, sessions, workshops, and demos will play a crucial role throughout the duration of the project. The consortium plans to organize three workshops and a number of sessions, such as panels, demos, presentations, 2 training sessions, during the course of the project.

The first technical workshop will be planned for M18, while the other two are planned for M24 and M36. There will be an emphasis on organizing face-to-face events but also depending on the feasibility of the conditions, it will be decided whether to organize a remote event or a physical one.

Dedicated and active participation in conferences and workshops co-located with major events to engage with relevant 6G initiatives and other SNS projects will be an emphasis. Precise timing of these events will be decided during the course of the project, but sufficiently in advance to allow in-depth preparation and will include events such as EUCNC, GlobeCom, Mobile World Congress etc.

HORSE maintains an internal events overview where upcoming important events are catalogued. Already since the official kickoff of the project, HORSE has participated (and plans to) and presented at:

- ETSI Research conference – Poster presentation by Coordinator Prof. Fabrizio Granelli, CNIT
- Mobile World Congress 2023, Barcelona – participation by communication and dissemination partner Martel
- SNS Lunchtime Webinar organized by the SNS JU – Presentation by Coordinator Prof. Fabrizio Granelli, CNIT
- EuCNC 2023, Gothenburg, Sweden - Poster presentation by Coordinator Prof. Fabrizio Granelli, CNIT

Following are some social media cards that we have created for the publicity of these participations.

Figure 17: Social media card for ETSI Research conference participation

Figure 18: Social media card for SNS webinar series participation

4.3.1 Targeted External Events

HORSE will be presented at a number of events with the goal of promoting and communicating all relevant information that will increase the project's visibility through all relevant means and tools. Participation in events also provides an opportunity to expand and strengthen the network of relevant parties interested in becoming a member of the HORSE audience.

HORSE's representation at the events will take place in different ways, including paper or project presentations, poster presentations, simple participation for liaising or networking

purposes, workshop organization or general support. Promotional materials such as brochures (where relevant) will be also used for dissemination purposes. The consortium has identified a number of events highly relevant to HORSE that will be the target for organizing workshop sessions, presenting in, or participating in (see Table 4).

Table 4: Targeted external events

Event	Date & Location	Type of audience	Planned Activities
CCW	23-25 May 2023, Helsinki, Finland	Scientific community, industry leaders, policy makers	Attendance, networking, synergies
EuCNC & 6G Summit	6-9 June 2023, Gothenburg, Sweden	Scientific community, industry leaders, policy makers	Joint workshop with other R&I SatCom Projects; Joint booth with other R&I SatCom Projects
ESA Space2Connect	7-9 June 2023, Matera, Italy	Scientific community, industry leaders, policy makers	Participation for liaising and networking purposes. Synergies between 6G-NTN and ESA ARTES funded project will be explored.
FIWARE Global Summit	12-13 June 2023, Vienna, Austria	Open source and scientific community, industry leaders, policy makers	Attendance, networking, synergies
3GPP RAN#100 and SA#100	12-16 June 2023, Taipei, Taiwan	Scientific community, industry leaders, policy makers	Release-19 Work Item definition
European Space Forum	5-6 July 2023, Brussels, Belgium	Scientific community, industry leaders, policy makers	Attendance, networking, synergies
Connected Britain	20-21 September 2023, London, UK	Scientific community, industry leaders, policy makers	Attendance, networking, synergies
European Wireless	2-4 October 2023, Rome, Italy	Scientific community, industry leaders, policy makers	Attendance, networking, synergies

Event	Date & Location	Type of audience	Planned Activities
IEEE Future Networks World Forum	13-15 November 2023, Baltimore, USA	Scientific community, industry leaders, policy makers	Attendance, networking, synergies
ICC 2024: IEEE International Conference on Communications	Rome, Italy	Scientific community, industry leaders, policy makers	Attendance, networking, synergies

4.4 Journals and Scientific Publications

HORSE partners have set a target of publishing on average 5 peer-reviewed publications per year in journals, conferences, and workshops. Table 5 below presents the relevant publications which will be considered for submission. We expect this list to be further reviewed and populated in the upcoming months as the academic and research partners take a deeper dive in HORSE results, methodologies, and challenges, which may be relevant for the scientific community. All scientific publications issued by the consortium will be made available through the website of the project, where a specific section has already been created.

Table 5: Scientific journals in HORSE’s scope

Publication Type	Submission To
Scientific peer reviewed publication	European 6G Annual Journal
Scientific peer reviewed publication	IEEE Global Communications Conference
Scientific peer reviewed publication	IEEE International Communications Conference
Scientific peer reviewed publication	Elsevier Journal of Information Security and Applications
Scientific peer reviewed publication	Advanced Satellite Multimedia Systems Conference (ASMS)
Scientific peer reviewed publication	IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management
Scientific peer reviewed publication	Elsevier Computer Networks

Together with the EU emblem, all 6G SNS projects, as part of the SNS JU, should add the following disclaimer:

“Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

4.5 Contributions to Open Source Initiatives and Standards

The HORSE project aims to contribute to open-source initiatives and standards, recognizing their importance in the digital supply chain. This commitment is expected to have a significant impact on the growth and consolidation of open-source development communities, as well as on standardization efforts. HORSE will make specific contributions to open source initiatives, such as ETSI OSM, OpenDaylight, ZeroTouch, and ECSO, among others. The project will adopt an open-source approach, distributing its work early on and making it accessible through open repositories and reports.

HORSE's contributions to open-source communities are significant in scale, addressing the issue of open-source security and providing a complete dossier on zero-day attacks and advanced persistent cyber threats. The project aims to target 50% of open-source solutions developed in the context of multi-vendor interoperability. Furthermore, the project's contributions are aimed at various target groups, including open-source communities, international security fora, cybersecurity experts and providers, penetration testers, system administrators, and cloud providers.

The HORSE project is committed to creating tangible outputs, including implementations, showcases and demonstrations, significant inputs to standardization activities, and the creation of commercially exploitable intellectual properties. All partners will participate in and contribute to several standardization and open-source initiatives, including Linux Foundation's ONAP, Akraino, and Anuket, and ETSI's OSM and TFS, among others. The consortium is committed to maximizing the industrial impact of the project results in the European and worldwide landscape, promoting the adoption of project results in standards organizations, open-source communities, and groups defining policies related to smart network services and their security capabilities. The project holds a dedicated task for standardization (Task 6.3), aiming to contribute to current and future standardization efforts and policy evolution.

Regarding Standardization, HORSE aims to establish industry standards for the solutions and frameworks developed in the project, in order to encourage global adoption of the researched technologies. To maximize this impact, the HORSE team will supervise relevant communities such as ETSI, IETF, 3GPP or GSMA.

To achieve this goal, HORSE will contribute to these communities ensuring the maximum impact of the technical project results. WP6 will track the work done with the different standardization groups, where all partners are involved in identifying and participating in any opportunities to contribute to technical documents specifications, working groups, software, proof of concepts and whitepapers.

5 Impact Assessment

To assess the impact of HORSE achievements, a number of indicators will be measured and evaluated in different phases of project implementation with the following objectives:

- Evaluating the degree of end users' satisfaction with the HORSE solution and components;
- Updating and assessing the detailed indicators with qualitative and quantitative measures;
- Assessing the impact of the final outcomes of the project.

5.1 Quantitative Indicators

HORSE Impact Creation Plan will be closely monitored throughout the duration of the project. The evaluation will be carried out on a regular basis to ensure the success of the project. A set of KPIs has been defined to measure the impact and conduct the most accurate assessment of the communication and dissemination activities. Table 6 presents the KPIs, their relevance to the tools/channels used, and the estimated target value, while Table 7 lists the deliverables within WP6.

Table 6: HORSE's communication KPIs

Tool/activity	KPI	Target value
Website	Unique visitors average (yearly)	>3000
Social media	Number of followers (by project end) on Twitter Number of followers (by project end) on LinkedIn	500 150
White papers	Number of published white papers	3
News items on website	Number of published news items	≥ 20
e-Newsletters	Number of newsletters sent out	6
Flyers/Brochures Presentations Posters/Roll-Ups	Number of flyers/brochures (incl. digital brochures) Number of project presentations Number of produced posters/roll-ups	3 6 3
Videos	Number of produced videos	6
Workshops	Number of attended/organized workshops	3
Webinars, panels, demos	Webinars Panels Demos	3+ 3+ 3+
Trainings (online/in-person)	Number of courses offered	2

Tool/activity	KPI	Target value
Scientific publications	Number of publications	15+
Participation in events & presentations	Number of external events partners attended to promote the project, events per including scientific conferences, and year industrial technology venues	5 per year
Standardization contributions	Number of contributions to standardization fora	6
Open-source contributions	Number of contributions to open-source initiatives	3
Policy strategies contributions	Number of policies contributed with recommendations	>3

5.2 Qualitative Indicators

Additionally, there are other positive results that cannot be easily measured since they cannot be quantified. Thus, in order to better measure the overall impact of the dissemination plan we will use the following qualitative indicators:

- **Proactive online community.** Social network dissemination efforts will ensure an interesting outcome in terms of discussion, feedback and content sharing and engagement.
- **Press/media coverage.** Distribution of press releases and publication of articles are geared to achieve press/media coverage about the project.
- **Long-term influence.** Sometimes the impact takes longer than just an immediate reaction. Therefore, it is expected that the "seed" scattered at the beginning will be "harvested" quite later. This will be considered when monitoring the impact of the project.

5.3 Planned Deliverables

Table 7 below lists the planned deliverables for the Impact Creation work package of HORSE.

Table 7: List of planned deliverables for the Impact Creation Work Package

Number	Name	Lead partner	Dissemination level	Due date
D6.1	Impact Creation Strategy and Plan	MARTEL	PU	M05
D6.2	Impact creation report and exploitation strategy	MARTEL	PU	M18
D6.3	Final impact creation report and exploitation plan	8BELLS	PU	M36

Conclusions and Next Steps

Deliverable 6.1 Impact Creation Strategy and Plan has been developed to provide guidelines and a consistent framework for all planned project activities to ensure HORSE's broad visibility, adequate promotion, and uptake of its results. The document at hand presents the initial communication, dissemination, and community building strategy, describes various activities conducted between M1 and M5, and outlines the planned promotional activities for the coming months. Developing this strategy at the early stages of the project will allow HORSE to maximize the impact of communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement activities and sustain the concepts, achievements, and knowledge developed throughout the project.

The goal of this plan is to guarantee that:

- All outreach activities follow the guidelines and are executed within the planned schedule,
- The messages are consistent and of a high standard,
- All consortium members contribute to promoting the project.

A monitoring and evaluation framework has been defined to measure the achieved progress and impact of the proposed strategy. Deliverables 6.2 and 6.3 will provide details on the progress of the strategy, achieved KPIs, attended and organized events, and the effectiveness of HORSE's online presence at M18 and M36 respectively.

Appendix A

WHAT IS A BRAND IDENTITY?

A brand identity allows you to recognize a consistent look and feel across all outlets (electronic and printed visual media). It defines how those who come into contact with the brand should perceive it and influences their opinion of the brand. This document lists and explains the visual identity elements of the HORSE project. These are rules and values to help you create and compose visual designs using its identity.

Examples of Horse's brand identity across different outlets (Twitter and LinkedIn accounts, website).

LOGO

Main version of the HORSE logo with some basic recommendations.

Main version

Clear zone

Icon version (for social media outlets)

Minimum size

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2

LOGO VARIATIONS

The main logo is also provided in the variations depicted here below, to allow readability over dark backgrounds or for black and white printing purposes.

Grey shades version

Negative version

Negative version 2

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DOS AND DONT'S

Basic instructions on how to use the main logo - and its variations - over diferent types of backgrounds.

Dos

Negative version on high contrasted background colour

Main version on image background assuring high contrast

Donts

Not enough contrasted background

Not enough contrasted background

CORPORATE COLOURS

A main palette of two colours based on the logo colour scheme plus a third complementary and warmer colour to highlight elements. Two more complementary greyscale colours complete the full HORSE colour palette.

For slide presentations and deliverables: the colour of standard elements has been defined and locked in the respective templates, as those documents are likely to be mainly edited outside design departments. To change colours (icons or additional text), editors will find the corporate color palette in the templates.

Palette of corporate colors

C90 M65 Y18 K4
R44 G87 B143
HEX #2c578f

C76 M32 Y0 K0
R37 G173 B223
HEX #25addf

C1 M48 Y100 K0
R242 G150 B0
HEX #f29600

C64 M41 Y33 K16
R97 G121 B137
HEX #617989

C27 M19 Y19 K4
R192 G193 B196
HEX #c0c1c4

FONT TYPES

HORSE's brand uses the open source fonts Dosis bold for headings and Open Sans for the body copy.

This applies to the website and all promotional material.

For presentations and deliverables, the system font Calibri (only Regular and Bold versions) should be used instead to avoid missing font issues, as those documents are likely to be mainly edited outside design departments.

Headings (to be used on the website and all promotional material)

Orbitron bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklm-nopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Body copy (to be used on the website and all promotional material)

Open Sans regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Open Sans bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Alternative Body copy and headings (to be used for presentations and deliverables)

Calibri regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Calibri bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

EC ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

All the EC funded projects should clearly show the acknowledgement to the EC fund in all Dissemination & Communication materials (e.g. flyers, posters, brochures, video, website, etc). Below you'll find a few examples of the elements to show in different positions.

Co-funded by the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union

CONTACTS

For any questions regarding the HORSE graphic assets and the uses you would like to make of them, do not hesitate to contact Miguel Alarcón at Martel Innovate:
miguel.alarcon@martel-innovate.com

All HORSE graphic assets, including this brand guidelines and the fonts, can be downloaded on the repository of the project.

Co-funded by the European Union

Appendix B

HOLISTIC, OMNIPRESENT, RESILIENT SERVICES FOR FUTURE 6G WIRELESS AND COMPUTING ECOSYSTEMS (HORSE)

Prof. Fabrizio Granelli
SNS Luncheon Webinar, Feb. 23, 2023, online

horse-6g.eu

PROJECT OVERVIEW

- **Project Name:** Holistic, Omnipresent, Resilient Services for Future 6G Wireless and Computing Ecosystems (HORSE)
- **Project website:** horse-6g.eu
- **Stream:** SNS Phase 1 (2022) Stream B
- **Members:** CNIT, ATOS, Ericsson, UPC, TUBS, Telefonica, NKUA, Suite5, EFACEC, ZORTE, 8-BELLS, HOLO-LIGHT, STS, Martel
- **Coordinator:** Fabrizio Granelli (CNIT, ITALY)
- **Other:** 6G infrastructure operation for smart connectivity and service management, 2 use cases: light transportation & extended reality

THE 6G SCENARIO

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3

THE 6G HORSE HOLISTIC SCENARIO

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4

HORSE KEY OBJECTIVES

Project Key Objectives:

- Comprehensive analysis of foreseeable 6G scenarios
- Designing the necessary end-to-end security solutions
- Development of a human-centric, holistic, omnipresent, and resilient smart services management and operation programmable platform
- Deploying AI technologies driving a completely predictive approach to security management, fully addressing high services, systems, risks, and threats dynamicity
- Characterize the user profile and the 6G system as a digital twin, to feed the AI distributed decision processes
- Designing the system interface to be intent-based to implement the role of the “Human-In-The-Loop”
- Deploy, demonstrate and validate HORSE in selected use cases
- Creating impact and promoting of open access to the HORSE platform for broad and sustainable exploitation of results

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HORSE ARCHITECTURE

The Intent-Based Interface (IBI) is responsible for mapping high-level intents into security workflows able to react to security threats and vulnerabilities, which will itself use AI for intent optimisation:

- Maintaining the «Human-in-the-Loop»
- Understanding service demands

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6

HORSE USE CASES

Secure Smart Light Rail Transit Systems

Remote Rendering to Power XR Industrial

Use case objective	KPI	Target
Resilience and disaster recovery	Down Time	Improve the down time in 50%
Resilience and disaster recovery (remotely operation)	Availability	Improve the availability in 20%
Decision support system	Statistics availability time	Capability to calculate the operation statistics data almost in real-time.

Use Case objective	KPI	Target
Detection of Design Fault	Decrease of errors	- 90% faults
Cost reduction of prototypes	Reductions of costs	- 50% costs
Faster time-to-market	Faster release of the product	+ 20% faster release on the market

Use Case	Final applications	HORSE (Security provisioning)	HORSE (Intelligence)
Secure Smart LRT Systems (SS-LRT)	Secure distributed operation: Fast recovery and timely failures detection.	Service management: A threat is detected and/or predicted and the secure orchestrator launches the actions to properly react.	Facilities: Models running on the DT pre-assess the actions to be taken to evaluate the expected performance, considering a highly distributed scenario.
Remote Rendering to Power XR Industrial (R²XRI)	Secure and reliable communication: Secure offloading and secure multiuser remote interaction.	Service management: HORSE will provide a secure multiuser environment for teleoperation, supporting a secure and flexible 6G components orchestration.	Facilities: Infrastructure modelling, considering the strict constraints imposed by XR (ultra-low latency and highly dense contexts), as well as the attacks models driven by global XR devices availability.

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HORSE WORK PLAN

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HORSE GANTT CHART

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PLANNED STANDARDIZATION ACTIVITIES

Potential targeted standardization bodies / groups:

- IETF WGs (I2NSF, SACM, ACME, PPM)
- ETSI MEC, NFV, ENI, ZSM, SAI
- 3GPP, SA3 (security) and SA5 (management aspects)
- ITU-T FGAN (Focus Group on Autonomous Networks)
- Open source: Linux Foundation ONAP, Akraino, Anuket, ETSI OSM and TFS
- Open source / open specs: OpenConfig, O-RAN

Standardization planning and estimated time plan:

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THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION

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